

The Art and Science of Teaching Speaking Skills

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the key principles and strategies for educators to effectively teach speaking skills in a classroom setting also we identified some aspects of teaching speaking. Is not merely about mastering language; it encompasses the development of confidence, clarity, and cultural sensitivity.

Effective communication lies at the heart of human interaction, making speaking skills a fundamental aspect of education across cultures and disciplines. Just as Harmer said to facilitate students with the 'new' language, teachers should have students exposed to the language, understand its meaning, understand its form (how it is constructed) and practice it [1;37]. Speaking skills are essential for both personal and professional success. Whether in everyday conversations, presentations, negotiations, or public speaking engagements, the ability to articulate ideas clearly and persuasively is invaluable. Proficient speakers not only convey information effectively but also engage and inspire their audience.

According to Kayi speaking refers to the gap between linguistic expertise and teaching methodology. Linguistic expertise concerns with language structure and language content. Teaching speaking is not like listening, reading, and writing. It needs habit formation because it is a real communication and speaking is a productive skill so it needs practicing as often as possible [2;65]

We do speaking in order to communicate with each other. Better communication means better understanding of others and us. Communication is a continuous process of expression, interpretation, and negotiation. The opportunities for communications are infinite and include systems of signs and symbols [4;10]. Communication requires a sender, a receiver and a medium. It can be said that both hearers and speakers do interactions by giving responds to what they have heard and listened to. Generally, people who encounter others through this oral communication have a certain goal that they want to achieve, the goal that underlies people to do the communication.

According to Nunan there are some principles for teaching speaking. Some of which are described below:

1. Give students practice with both fluency and accuracy. At the beginning and intermediate level of studies, learners must be given opportunities to improve their fluency as well as accuracy. Accuracy means using the target language correctly and fluency is using language quickly and confidently. The teacher should not emphasize on any one aspect of speaking. Rather, students should get practice on both accuracy and fluency.

2. Use group work or pair work. To improve students' speaking, they should be given enough opportunities to speak in class. So, teacher talk time should be less and student talk time should be more. It is important for language teachers do not take up all the time. According to Nunan also, "Pair work and group work can be used to increase the amount of time that learners get to speak in the target language during lesson." In this way, the students will get chance to interact and practice the language with other students [3;77]

Now we look through some key Principles of Teaching Speaking.

Authentic communication is undeniable part because teachers should encourage students to engage in meaningful conversations that simulate real-life situations. This could involve discussions, debates, role-plays, or presentations on topics relevant to their interests and experiences. In the next step building confidence is considered as a crucial one. Creating a supportive environment leads to students feel comfortable expressing themselves without fear of judgment. Provide constructive feedback to help them improve gradually. Language Fluency and Accuracy is help to keep balance fluency (the ability to speak smoothly and coherently) with accuracy (correct grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation). Incorporate activities that focus on both aspects to develop well-rounded speaking skills. Listening Skills are helpful in terms of effective speaking with active listening. Teach students to listen attentively, ask clarifying questions, and respond appropriately to others, promoting a more dynamic and interactive speaking environment. Cultural Awareness is serves as deeply intertwined with culture. Encourage students to consider cultural nuances in their speech, such as tone, gestures, and etiquette, to communicate effectively across different contexts.

Strategies for Teaching Speaking

1. Structured Activities: Use structured activities like debates, group discussions, interviews, and presentations to provide opportunities for speaking practice. These activities can be tailored to different proficiency levels and learning objectives.

2. Role-plays and Simulations: Engage students in role-plays to simulate real-life scenarios, such as customer interactions, job interviews, or academic discussions. This helps them apply language in practical contexts and enhances their problem-solving skills.

3. Peer Feedback: Incorporate peer evaluation sessions where students provide constructive feedback to each other. This encourages active listening, critical thinking, and collaborative learning.

4. Technology Integration: Leverage technology tools such as video recording for self-assessment, online forums for asynchronous discussions, or virtual reality simulations for immersive language practice.

5. Vocabulary and Pronunciation: Integrate activities that specifically target vocabulary expansion and pronunciation practice. Vocabulary games, word banks, and pronunciation drills can help students improve their speaking fluency and clarity.

6. Assessment and Feedback. Assessment should be ongoing and multifaceted, focusing on both fluency and accuracy. Consider using rubrics that assess speaking skills based on criteria such as coherence, vocabulary usage, pronunciation, and interaction with others. Provide specific feedback that highlights strengths and areas for improvement, encouraging students to reflect on their progress and set goals for further development.

Teaching speaking is a very important part of foreign language learning. The ability to communicate in a foreign language clearly and efficiently contributes to the success of the learner in school and success later in every phase of life. Therefore, it is essential that foreign language teachers' pay great attention to teaching speaking by providing students with

adequate exposure with the language and with adequate motivation to communicate through it. Rather than leading students to pure memorization, providing a rich environment where meaningful communication takes place is desired. With this aim, teacher should be aware of the problems that may face in conducting the English speaking class; starts from the problem faced by the students and the teachers, in addition, the problem from the language itself that is not spoken in the community [5].

So, teaching speaking skills is a dynamic process that requires creativity, patience, and a deep understanding of language acquisition principles. By fostering a supportive learning environment, integrating diverse speaking activities, and providing constructive feedback, educators can empower students to become confident and effective communicators in diverse personal and professional settings. Embrace the art and science of teaching speaking, and watch as your students flourish in their ability to connect, persuade, and inspire through the power of language. Various speaking techniques such as those listed above can contribute a great deal to students in developing basic interactive skills necessary for life. Hopefully, these activities make students more active to speak in the target language in the learning process and at the same time make their learning more meaningful and fun for them. Embrace the art and science of teaching speaking, and watch as your students flourish in their ability to connect, persuade, and inspire through the power of language.

References:

1. Harmer, Jeremy. 1998. How to Teach Language: An Introduction to the Practice of English Language Teaching p37. Addison Wesley Longman Limited.
2. Kayi, Hayriye. 2006. Teaching Speaking: Activities to Promote Speaking in a Second Language p65. University of Nevada. The Internet TESL Journal, Vol. XII, No. 11,
3. Nunan, David. 2003. Practical English Language Teaching p77. NY:McGraw-Hill
4. Savignon, Sandra J. 1993. Communicative Competence: Theory and Classroom Practice, Texts and Contexts in Second Language Learning p10. Urbana. Addison Wesley Publishing Company, Inc
5. file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/rigel,+Journal+editor,+G+VOL+2+NOPRIANUS++105+-+128.pdf